

Stakeholder User Stories - RDA Minimal MD

	A	B	C
1	User story #	User story	Stakeholder
2			
3	1	Learner searching for training for specific skills	Learner
4	2	Trainer looking for training resources for their own training	Trainer
5	3	Service provider wanting to promote their training resources	Service provider
6	4	Service Provider wanting to know where gaps are in subject coverage	Service provider
7	5	A researcher looking for training (basic, intermediate or expert)	Researcher
8	6	Trainer looking for existing modules to combine for a new course	Trainer
9	7	Trainers looking for resources in a given language	Trainer
10	8	Funder wanting to know which training resources have been created by a specific project	Funder
11	9	Developer wanting to add to or create web interface	Developer
12	10	Learner wanting to find materials from a course	Learner
13	11	Developer wanting to import metadata into a different catalog	Developer
14	12	A trainer wanting to share their materials	Trainer
15	13	Learner searching for specific type of LR, i.e. MOOC, self-study, webinar, F2F training opportunities	Learner
16	14	Service provider wanting to provide an overview of training possibilities for their community	Service provider
17	15	Learner looking for free courses on a specific topic	Learner
18	16	Developer looking to reuse data about OER objects for different application	Developer